

USE OF DIDACTIC GAME METHOD IN TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO SPEECH

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***Abstract.** Opinions and some theories about the importance of using the didactic game method in teaching primary school students to speak were used to elaborate the content of this article.*

***Keywords:** Mother tongue, language, nutty activity, didactic games, speech training, linguistic competence, expression of opinion.*

Increasing the level of speech activity of students is an urgent issue in the rapidly developing educational system. Therefore, it is permissible to take into account many aspects in increasing the speech activity of students studying in primary education. Didactic games also help the teacher in this. This is based on the fact that the age characteristics of students of primary school age are considered the most favorable for starting education. For this reason, the first years of school are important in preparing a child for adult life.

Today, the teacher fully meets the goals set, helps to create motivation for the formation of linguistic competence in his students, ensures the formation of elements of attention, imagination and memory, the student is conscious of his actions. should choose effective teaching methods for the development of forms of management, mental activity and interest. It should not be forgotten that the ability to create a comfortable and friendly atmosphere in the classroom among students, to treat their peers carefully, to show kindness and attention is an integral part of the successful completion of any task in the educational process. . The game method can be a good solution to this problem, because at the primary school age, the game becomes one of the main activities of the child. In addition, the child's abilities are fully revealed during the game, and the game includes a certain educational potential in addition to the entertainment function. Therefore, the use of the game method in educational processes can help in the learning process of primary school students. In this regard, the game plays a special role in the development of speaking skills of primary school students, because it encourages students to make oral statements, adds color to each lesson, and arouses the interest of students. possible

At the stage of primary education, language should be considered as a tool for the development of the child's personality, taking into account his abilities, interests and motivations. Through communication and activities in the mother tongue, students develop these characteristics, that is, every student of primary school age learns, learns both the world and himself, in the process of learning the mother tongue will have spiritual wealth to be given to students. In this regard, teaching the mother tongue at the primary level has several goals, such as communicative, educational, general education and development. Before considering the communicative purpose of learning, it is necessary to take into account the specific features of the "mother tongue". The peculiarity of this science is that "language, whether it is a native language or a foreign language, is a means of communication in the natural conditions of social life, receiving and transmitting information about the surrounding reality. The next feature of this subject is not to add knowledge about the surrounding objects and phenomena of reality that

students can get while teaching it, but to expand the imagination of the national culture of the country through the language and to expand the general outlook. is implied.

The educational goal of teaching the mother tongue is for students to learn to listen and hear each other, to treat each other with respect. Also, teaching this subject allows for aesthetic education, because children like to listen to language speeches, pronounce different words, learn poems and sing songs. All this can be achieved by using didactic games in the teaching processes organized in the native language classes within the primary education subjects in the formation of students' linguistic competences. The educational goal of teaching the mother tongue is to master new means of expression, new grammatical structures, to expand philological and general aspects, to go deeper into the subject being studied.

In turn, the developmental goal in teaching the mother tongue is also important. In this case, the developmental goal of teaching is to involve students in activities that develop their emotional perception, intellectual, mobile, emotional-volitional and motivational spheres.

The teacher should take into account the importance of understanding the educational goals for each of them separately and in their interdependence, because it is impossible to achieve the educational result without defining the goals.

In accordance with the state general education standard of primary general education, the results of mastering the main educational program in the mother tongue reflect the following, which is very helpful in achieving a high educational result:

mastering the basic skills of oral and written communication with native speakers, mastering speech skills and needs based on them, as well as the rules of speech and non-speech behavior;

mastering basic language concepts necessary for mastering oral and written speech in the language at the elementary level, expanding linguistic outlook;

forming a friendly attitude and tolerance towards speakers based on the introduction of acquaintance with the life of peers, children's folklore and existing examples of children's fiction into the course of the lesson.

In addition, important results are highlighted in specific areas of language acquisition, such as communicative, cognitive, value-oriented, aesthetic, and labor. The most important area is the communicative area, because the goal of teaching the most necessary components of the language at the initial stage is the formation of elementary communicative competence. It is known that the communicative sphere includes: speech, language and socio-cultural competences. Through these communicative abilities, the level of development of linguistic competence and the result of mastering linguistic concepts are shown.

Thus, when teaching primary school students to speak, it is necessary to take into account the specific features of this subject. In addition, it is necessary to rely on the goals, the main one of which is the communicative goal, because the students need to master the language as a means of communication. It should also be noted that it is impossible to achieve results without learning goals.

The educational possibilities of the game method in the educational process have been known for a long time. The effectiveness of using the game method has been noted by many scientists involved in language teaching. This is explained by the fact that the abilities of any person, especially a child, are fully and sometimes unexpectedly revealed during the game.

There are many definitions of play. According to the definition of M.F.Stronin: "Game is a type of activity in situations aimed at restoring and mastering social experience, in which self-control of behavior is formed and improved.»

A game is a type of social practice, an effective reproduction of life events outside of a real practical environment. It always appears in two dimensions of time: present and future, providing momentary joy and also serving urgent personal needs. Life situations are modeled in it. The game also strengthens the characteristics, qualities, situations, skills, and abilities necessary for a person to perform social, professional and creative functions.

So, it can be said that on the basis of these theories, in order to increase the level of speech activity of students studying in primary school, it is necessary to organize lesson processes accordingly, without losing sight of the information presented in the theories. Also, it is necessary to know how to sort and summarize the types of didactic games that can ensure the effectiveness of the use of didactic games in teaching elementary school students to speak, and how to use them in accordance with the topic of the organized lesson. This will only help to achieve the goal of teaching students to speak.

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